

CRIMINALIZATION OF POLITICS: STRUGGLING TO FIGHT IN LAW AND JUSTICE**Nitya Nand Pandey*****Abstract**

Offence is an offence, whether it is in society or in the service sector, in profession or in business or in the political arena, but 'criminalization of politics' is the subject of most concern and debate and should be so because politics, at national as well as states level, is something which provides base to the democratic setup in our country. Criminalization of politics, leaving behind many other burning issues in the country, has become so vivid in this time that on this subject, the Supreme Court of India and the Law Commission have been active with great concern. On one hand, the judiciary is earmarking solutions to this vivid problem through the Election Commission and the Law Commission and on the other hand the Legislature is not leaving any stone unturned to provide protection to it. Under these circumstances, the fear is now being expressed that 'criminalization of politics' is creating the background of the conflict between law and justice? In fact, this topic has long been the subject of debate before the Supreme Court, and whenever the judiciary has tried to solve this problem - then the legislature has tried to obstruct the path of that solution. However, it is different that every time the legislature has to respect the verdict of judiciary.

Introduction

Since the criminalization of politics is now again moving towards its peak, it is again the reason for discussion and debate before the court. The 244th Report of the Law Commission, 2014, which is about the "disability related to elections", is actually a "brief document" on 'criminalization of politics' and to understand the seriousness of the subject, such remarks of the Commission are sufficient which states that "the criminalization of politics has become so widespread that its treatment is urgently needed".

In fact, the Supreme Court is considering the matter along with other topics in a public interest litigation called *Public Interest Foundation and the other Vs. Union of India and another (writ petition number 536 years 2011)* and on December 16, 2013, while hearing the petition, the court asked for the suggestions from the Law Commission regarding the election reforms for the decriminalization of politics and for prohibiting the tendency to present false affidavits during elections. This report of the Law Commission is the result of the same suggestion. Although the report has been submitted to the Supreme Court and special remarks on the subject will be hasty, but the issues which have been expressed by the Supreme Court, along with the Law Commission itself, and whose people are being victimized day by day, and in some cases the credibility of the country has also been shrouded in the world, and when, except the criminals of politics, the rest of the people are feeling helpless, then the subject may not be leaved by considering it less important.

It cannot be denied that offence is an offence, whether it is in society or in the service sector, in profession or in business or in the political arena, but 'criminalization of politics' is the subject of most concern and debate and should be so because politics, at national as well as states level, is something which provides base to the democratic setup in our country. Because this area which establishes the rule of law in the country as well as in the states, and also leads the movement of the democratic government, which must be crimeless, selfless and democratic.

In fact, the possibility of criminalization of politics in the country was experienced before independence. This is the reason why a new chapter, Chapter IX-A was added to the Indian Penal Code, 1860 through an amendment, in British India in the year 1920. This chapter is about the offences relating to election' and it spread over Section 171-A to 171-I. The possible main election offences were made punishable under this chapter. Then, the offences under this chapter was based on the involvement of any 'candidate' and 'voters' of the election and on the activities which were influencing or affecting the 'voting' like bribery, undue influence, impersonation or fabrication, hospitality, misrepresentation, etc., or failure in presenting the material documents were considered as crime, which is still in the pages of the law and is still prevalent in elections. But this time the subject matter of concern is more serious and comprehensive than these acts, and that is the candidate of the election is himself is accused of many crimes as per his affidavit. It is true that the charge does not make anyone guilty, and the perception of being the culprit can be made only after conviction, but the question is, can such a convicted person be an active candidate in the elections, only because their appeal against the conviction is pending....?

There is also a harsh reality that then crimes in the politics was secretly done, and today political crimes and other related offences are openly done or even such allegations are being made openly. Then the

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question was, how to keep criminals away from the elections? Today the question is, 'How can criminals can be eliminated from the elections (politics)?'

In fact, 25 years before independence, Shri C. Rajagopalachari had expressed this prospect in his 'Prison Diary' with this declaration that "as soon as we will be given freedom, elections and their corruption, injustices and tyrannical rule of wealth and impactlessness in the administration will make life a hell. "In today's context, the expression shows its relevancy and its words seem to be meaningful and visible.

Although constitutional makers and legislators tried to curb 'criminalization of politics' through Article 102/191 of the Constitution and Article 8 of the Representation of the People Act, 1951, but the spark of crime in politics which was sparked off in the 1970s has now been blazed and all the efforts to to quench it was futile. On the other hand, while keeping in mind the principle of keeping the foundations of crime in politics, "Yeh-Ken" has kept its intention of sticking to the power, while keeping the proverb in "You put me down." Of course this is a contemplative topic.

As far as the graph of crime in politics is concerned, the comment made on this subject in the report of Vohra Committee in the year 1993 is that the contacts of bureaucrats, politicians and the media with the criminals are increasing rapidly and that criminals are running parallel government. According to the ADR Survey Report, 2014, which has also been made part of its report by the Law Commission, that in 10 years from 2004 to 2013 the number of criminal cases registered against the national / provincial election candidates were 18% i.e. out of total 62,847 persons, about 11,063 were charged with criminal offences. And about half of which, i.e. 5,253 were related to serious crimes (murder, rape, crime against women, corruption, organized crime). What is shocking is the fact that 1,181 of these candidates got elected either become MPs or MLAs, whose percentage is 13.5% of the total winning candidates.

In recent past of the 15th Lok Sabha which ended in February, 2014, 30% i.e. 162 MPs were having pending criminal proceedings on them, out of which 76 charges were of serious offences. In 2004 it was 24%. This means that in the 2009 election there has been an increase of 6%. The same situation is also of the legislative assemblies of the states of the country. Out of total MLAs of the different states of the country, about 31% i.e. 1258 out of 4032 were having the pending criminal proceedings against them, of which there are serious crimes against half of them. The most shocking facts of these are also the fact that the highest number of MLAs (47%) and one legislator have recorded the highest number of cases (36) in Uttar Pradesh. The most surprising fact in all of these is that the percentage of becoming an MPs / MLA was only 12% while the clean candidates contested in the election and 23% of the victorious MPs / MLAs were having criminal history. It is clear that presently, people having criminal history are more reaching the Parliament or Assembly than the good / clean candidates.

Not only this, the scenario of the 16th Lok Sabha elections 2014 in the country, instead of reducing all these figures, provides an extension. National Election Watch and Association for Democratic Reform (ADR), after conducting a survey-review of the affidavits submitted by the candidates themselves in the election, concludes that by the elections of 7 phases, nearly 3% more candidates were tainted and corrupted than the previous election (2009). In Uttar Pradesh itself, this figure is very high. Here, in the year 2009, where 215 candidates were corrupt and tainted, and in the elections of 2014, total 259 candidates were filed the election form out of which 215 were tainted, amongst which 185 were having the serious criminal charge on them. It is enough to tell that criminalization of the politics of the country is leading to a very broad and serious situation.

As far as the current constitutional / legal provisions are concerned to keep politics free from crime, Article 84 and 173 of the Constitution, where, respectively, mentions the qualifications of MPs and MLAs (Indian citizens, 25 years, other legal qualifications), then Article 102 And 191 deals with their disabilities, in which there is a disqualification, other than the disqualifications under any other law made by Parliament. For this purpose, the Representation of the People Act, 1951 is the main law of the political sector, under which MPs and MLAs contest elections and become victorious MP / MLA. Section 8 (1) (2) and (3) provides a list of crimes for which the convicted MPs or MLAs are declared unqualified for contesting elections or being MP / MLA. Section 8 (3) declares the disqualification of residual nature, in which there is a provision that if a candidate is punished with imprisonment of 2 years or more for a crime, then for 6 years from the date of conviction or for release, they will be disqualified to be a contestant in the election. But under the guise of Section 8 (4) which provides for an appellate provision, convicted MPs or MLAs, despite the conviction, are not only actively involved in politics, but also becoming MP / MLA by participating in the elections.

Thus, this Section 8 (4) of the Representation of the People Act provides protection to criminal MPs / MLAs and they continued to be a member of the Parliament and the Legislative Assembly. Ultimately, the Supreme Court gave a historic decision by declaring Section 8 (4) as unconstitutional in the case of *Lily Thomas v. Union of India (2013) 7 SCC 653*, and also declared that MPs and MLAs are disqualified right from the date of their conviction in accordance to Article 101 (3) / 190 (3) of the Constitution, and their post will be treated as vacant from that date. The effort to bring a bill in the Parliament has been made to neutralize this

decision. But this bill was withdrawn after a widespread protest against it, and hence, the possible dispute between the legislature and judiciary has been dropped out.

Still, it will be a disguise to presume that this decision will eliminate criminalization of politics. There are still many questions which are in disputes and the Supreme Court is considering them, out of which the most important question is to fight elections from prison which another reason for criminalization of politics. Although the Supreme Court had given a decision in relation to Lilly Thomas's decision (July 10, 2013) in the matter of *chief election commissioner, etc. Vs. Janak Pradhanider (People's Watch) and others (Civil appeal number 3040-3041 years 2004)* that under section 62 (5) of the Representation of the People Act, 1951, no person remains a 'voter' as long as he is imprisoned or in lawful police custody. He does not get the right to vote, so he is also not eligible to contest elections. The effect of this decision was that, the tendency of contesting elections from prison was almost stopped, but in order to neutralize this decision, the Parliament passed an amendment in the Representation of the People Act, 2013, which establish a system of contesting the elections from the prison. For this purpose, a proviso to Section 62 (5) have been added which provides that if a person's name has been entered in the voter's list, he will not be denied being a voter (Section 3). Apart from this, Section 4 has also been added through an amendment which states that in spite of any decision, order or decree, the provisions of the Representation of the People Act shall be prevailed.

It is obvious that on one side the judiciary is trying to remove the criminalization from politics, on the other hand, the legislature is trying to disable it. Now this Amendment Act has also been accepted by the Supreme Court for consideration. Now it is to see that whether this conflict between the law and justice will ends with a meaningful result or not.

In addition to the above, submission of false affidavits by candidates contesting in the elections is also an important issue which has maintained the presence of crime in the politics. In the case of *Union of India Vs. Association of Democratic Reforms (2002) 5 scc 294*, the Supreme Court had directed the Election Commission to take information on affidavits from the candidates participating in the parliament and assembly elections, regarding their educational, financial, especially criminal history, in which it is clearly mentioned that if the candidate has ever been convicted / released / indicted in any criminal offense, if yes so for what period, and also whether he has been accused in any such crime 6 months before enrollment or the charge against him is taken or the notice has been taken for the offences which is punishable with the penalty of 2 years or more. Then the court had justified this instruction that every citizen has the basic right under Article 19 (1) (a) to know the history of the candidates. At that time too, the Parliament had added the Section 33B by passing the Representation of the People (Third Amendment) Act, 2002 to neutralize this decision, which has been declared unconstitutional by the Supreme Court in the case of the *People's Union for Civil Liberties v. Union of India (2003) 2 SCC 549*, and the submission of 'affidavit' has become mandatory since then.

But this case did not end here. In order to avoid giving actual information about their crimes, now the candidates have started giving false information in the affidavit, which has been taken seriously by the Supreme Court and in this perspective also had sought the suggestions from the Law Commission. In the 244th Report, the Law Commission has suggested that the submission of false affidavit should be made punishable under section 125-A of the Representation of the People Act, and the penalty for it should be minimum of 2 years and it is also been suggested to declare this as a disqualification under Section 8 (1) of the Act. Of course, if this suggestion is accepted by the court and makes a decision, it can be helpful in reducing the criminalization of politics to a great extent.

Another important question, on which the Supreme Court had sought the opinion of the Law Commission, is that the candidate's disqualification from the election should be continue in the same manner, or it should be declared after the framing of the charges by the court or after the submission of the report by the investigating officer under section 173 of Criminal Procedure Code, 1973? The report of the Law Commission on this question is a balanced one. In the opinion of the Law Commission, the present inadequate legal provision of disqualification on the proof of the fault is not being effective in preventing criminalization in politics due to delays and delinquent conviction. Therefore, such cases should be speedily disposed of on the day-to-day basis within 1 year of the framing of the charges.

On the second supplementary question, the Commission suggests that with certain safeguards, the chargeability can be applied after the charge-fixing, but not on the basis of the report under Section 173. Under the security measures, the Commission believes that disqualification can be declared only after the framing of the charges in the offences which are punishable with the imprisonment of 5 years or more, and such disqualification should be continue till the release of the convicted or till the 6 years. On the basis of this, on March 10, 2014, the Supreme Court had directed in the matter of the *Public Interest Foundation Case* that the court should decide such matters of MPS/MLAs on the day-to-day basis within 1 year. And if this is not possible, then report it to the Chief Justice of the High Court and decide according to his direction. Although this case is not yet finalized and the public and intellectuals of the country still expect any historical decision from the court.

It can be concluded that the matter of criminalization of politics has, due to the enslavement of the people and the increasingly complexity, has now become a matter of legislature versus the judiciary. The legislature, whose constituents are MPs and MLAs, do not want to make any law by invoking an act that is dangerous for their own or restricts their freedom of working; on the other hand, the judiciary has its constitutional responsibility and "justice-provider image" due to which it is making every effort to curb such tendencies, due to which crime in politics is increasing. Whatever the situation / circumstance, "Satyamev Jayate" is a national thread sentence. It should be expected that all will contribute to the establishment of politics with clean, healthy, dignified and democratic rule.

